

Opportunities for Data Exchange

THE ODE PROJECT / DATA CENTRES

Opportunities for Data Sharing

There is a growing consensus in science, and society generally, that primary research data resulting from publicly funded research should be shared widely so that the maximum benefits can be gained from the investment. There are common barriers and some reluctance, but also powerful drivers and benefits related to putting this general principle into practice.

Why should you as a data centre manager care about data sharing?

With the ever increasing availability of data, the best way to ensure its sharing and re-use is becoming a prominent issue. Consequently the roles of data centres within this field are constantly growing. You need to be aware of the impact of your centre's services on your users.

Do you know about others' views?

The EU FP7-funded ODE project has collected views from numerous individuals – representative of all stakeholder groups involved – on the opportunities for data sharing. These views were analysed and consolidated in order to inform each group about each others' views and possible future activities.

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What ODE has learned:

Publishers are keen to work with data centres to ensure the long term availability and findability of data underlying the publications. Therefore, co-operation with libraries and data centres such as yours is important to be able to provide a common framework for data sharing.

Research funding agencies are increasingly putting an obligation for data management on their researchers. Data centres such as yours should provide the infrastructure to make this easier for data producers.

Data owners, however, admit that they hesitate to share their data because they do not see any benefit yet.

Libraries are aware that they need your experience in data management and providing services to develop tools and guidelines for researchers.

What you and your organization can do:

Data centres can advance research data management by providing training for data preparation. This should be developed in close co-operation with the data producers and owners to meet the needs of the research community and to help lower the potential barriers to data sharing.

New methods and tools are needed for data sharing and data preservation to ensure future access to linked data. In addition, specific access controls for sensitive and confidential data and user friendly submission processes should be developed. Citation formats and standards need to be implemented more widely, so that they can become an embedded part of the scholarly communication system.

New types of services should be implemented in co-operation with publishers and libraries. Above all, a common system of credit and recognition for data production and sharing is needed, and can be encouraged by providing researchers with clear instructions on how to cite data.

Data is the new gold.

"We have a huge goldmine... Let's start mining it."

Neelie Kroes, Vice-President of the European Commission responsible for the Digital Agenda
<http://europa.eu/rapid/pressReleasesAction.do?reference=SPEECH/11/872&type=HTML>

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